

Simultaneity in Physical Reality

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Abstract

This article explores the concept of simultaneity in physical reality by analyzing two central scenarios:

- (i) two events observed by a single observer, and
- (ii) one event observed by two different observers.

The focus is on light events, such as a lamp turning on and off. We explore the geometric and physical implications of the nature of simultaneity in these cases.

1 Introduction

1.1 Simultaneity in a general perspective

Simultaneity generally means that two or more events occur at exactly the same time. What is meant by "exactly the same time" depends on the concept of time we are using.

Historically and philosophically, the nature of simultaneity has been taken for granted in classical mechanics and in everyday thought. However, with advances in modern physics, this view has been challenged and changed.

1.2 Classical Physics (Newtonian Mechanics)

In classical physics, the nature of simultaneity is considered an absolute property. This means that if two events occur simultaneously according to one observer, they also occur simultaneously for all other observers, regardless of their position or motion.

Time was considered universal and common to all, a fundamental principle of Newtonian mechanics.

1.3 Special Theory of Relativity (Einstein, 1905)

Einstein's special theory of relativity from 1905 represented a **fundamental change** in the classical view of simultaneity. He showed that simultaneity is not an absolute property, but depends on the motion and frame of reference of the observer.

Two events that appear to occur simultaneously in one frame of reference (e.g., on Earth) may occur at different times in another frame of reference (e.g., on a fast-moving spaceship). This effect directly follows from the constancy of the speed of light in all inertial frames, independent of the observer's motion.

Simultaneity is a **fundamental** concept in physics and plays a **crucial role** in our understanding of time. In classical mechanics, the nature of simultaneity is considered absolute, but in the theory of relativity it is **relative** and dependent on the motion of the observer.

2 Simultaneity in our reality

2.1 Two events, one observer

Consider an observer O observing two events E_1 and E_2 . The two points where the events occur (E_1 and E_2) and the point where the observer is (O) form an inertial reference frame (IRF). The distances are equal: $E_1O = OE_2 = d$. We start by placing the observer exactly in the middle of the distance E_1E_2 . When the experiment begins, the clock in O is reset, $t(O) = 0$. Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

The observer records an event when the light pulse from it reaches him. The observer O records the time of the two events, $t(E_1)$ and $t(E_2)$. For simplicity, we denote the times as t_1 and t_2 in the figures, where $t_i \equiv t(E_i)$. We analyze three possible cases, always starting from Fig. 1.

(2.1.1) $t(E_1) = t(E_2)$: The system $E_1 - O - E_2$ is at absolute rest in space. Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

In this case, when the two light pulses reach the middle of the path at the same time, the two events are **simultaneous in an absolute sense** (regardless of what any other observers record).

$$t(E_1) = t(E_2) = \frac{d}{c}. \quad (1)$$

(2.1.2) $t(E_1) > t(E_2)$: The system $E_1 - O - E_2$ moves uniformly in the direction $E_1 \rightarrow E_2$. Fig. 3.

Fig. 3

It is the light pulse from E_2 that reaches O first.

We see that the distance $OE_2 = d = ct_2 + vt_2 = (c + v)t_2 \rightarrow$

$$t(E_2) = \frac{d}{c + v}. \quad (2)$$

We show and calculate the time t_1 when the light pulse from E_1 reaches O . During this time, the entire system has moved the distance vt_1 . Fig. 4.

Fig. 4

We see that the distance $E_1O = d = ct_1 - vt_1 = (c - v)t_1 \rightarrow$

$$t(E_1) = \frac{d}{c - v}. \quad (3)$$

(2.1.3) $t(E_1) < t(E_2)$: The system $E_1 - O - E_2$ moves uniformly in the direction $E_1 \leftarrow E_2$. Fig. 5.

Fig. 5

In this case, it is the light pulse from E_1 that reaches O first.

We see that the distance $E_1O = d = ct_1 + vt_1 = (c + v)t_1 \rightarrow$

$$t(E_1) = \frac{d}{c + v}. \quad (4)$$

We show and calculate the time t_2 when the light pulse from E_2 reaches O . During this time, the entire system has moved the distance vt_2 . See Fig. 6.

Fig. 6

We see that the distance $OE_2 = d = ct_2 - vt_2 = (c - v)t_2 \rightarrow$

$$t_2(E) = \frac{d}{c - v}. \tag{5}$$

We see that experiments in (2.1.2) (Fig. 3, Fig. 4) and (2.1.3) (Fig. 5, Fig. 6) are symmetric.

The above thought experiment shows that the nature of the simultaneity of two events recorded by an observer depends on:

- the position of the observer relative to these two events
- the absolute motion of the IRF (with respect to physical space)
- the relative motion between the observer and the events

Because multiple distinct scenarios exist, each case must be analyzed individually. A single universal formula for calculating the recorded times across all possible scenarios does not appear to exist.

As you can see, the above cases are the simplest, when the observer is on the same line formed by the two events. Otherwise, the positions form a triangle from which $t(E_1)$ and $t(E_2)$ can be calculated. Fig. 7.

Fig. 7

How should one think and act here? In order to be able to determine whether the two events are simultaneous, one must know the exact positions between the observer and the points where the events occur.

One calculates $t(E_1)$ and $t(E_2)$ from the model and then registers the actual times when the light pulse reaches the observer. If these are equal, the events are simultaneous (in an absolute sense) otherwise not.

If the observer has no means of measuring the distance and the position relative to the two points where the events occur and the two light pulses arrive at the same time, the observer perceives that the two events are simultaneous. But this "nature of simultaneity" means nothing. What can one do with that information?

Of course, the **nature of simultaneity is relative**, it depends on the observer's position relative to the two points in space where the events occur, on how the IRF where these points are located is in motion relative to each other and relative to the observer. Depending on the values of the two recorded times, the observer will say that the two events are **simultaneous** (if $t(E_1) = t(E_2)$) and that they are **not simultaneous** (if $t(E_1) \neq t(E_2)$). But this applies to an **ordinary observer**. A physicist/mathematician knows how to calculate the two times and determine whether the two events are **simultaneous in an absolute sense** or not. Then this applies to all observers! See 1.2. *But this is NOT about the special theory of relativity, SR.*

2.2 One event, two observers

Here we consider a single event E observed by two observers O_1 and O_2 . We place the point E where the event occurs midway between the two observers who synchronize their clocks at the beginning of each thought experiment. The times recorded by the two observers are denoted by $t_{O_1}(E)$ and $t_{O_2}(E)$, but we will write only t_1 and t_2 for simplicity both in the figures and in the text ($t_{O_i}(E) \equiv t_i(E) \equiv t_i$).

Fig. 8

(2.2.1) If both observers record the event at the same time according to their respective clocks, then

$$t_1(E) = t_2(E) = \frac{d}{c}. \quad (6)$$

Fig. 9

Then we say that the event E is **simultaneous in an absolute sense** for both observers.

(2.2.2) $t_1(E) < t_2(E)$: The system $O_1 - E - O_2$ moves in the direction $O_1 \rightarrow O_2$. Fig. 10.

Fig. 10

The light pulse from E first reaches the observer O_1 .

We see that the distance $O_1E = d = ct_1 + vt_1 = (c + v)t_1 \rightarrow$

$$t_1(E) = \frac{d}{c + v}. \quad (7)$$

We show and calculate the time t_2 when the light pulse from E reaches O_2 . During this time, the entire system has moved the distance vt_2 . Fig. 11.

Fig. 11

We see that the distance $EO_2 = d = ct_2 - vt_2 = (c - v)t_2 \rightarrow$

$$t_2(E) = \frac{d}{c - v}. \quad (8)$$

(2.2.3) $t_1(E) > t_2(E)$: The system $O_1 - E - O_2$ moves in the direction $O_1 \leftarrow O_2$. Fig. 12.

Fig. 12

The light pulse from E first reaches the observer O_2 .

We see that the distance $EO_2 = d = ct_2 + vt_2 = (c + v)t_2 \rightarrow$

$$t_2(E) = \frac{d}{c + v}. \quad (9)$$

We show and calculate the time t_1 when the light pulse from E reaches O_1 . During this time, the entire system has moved the distance vt_1 . See Fig. 13.

Fig. 13

We see that the distance $O_1E = d = ct_1 - vt_1 = (c - v)t_1 \rightarrow$

$$t_1(E) = \frac{d}{c - v}. \quad (10)$$

We see that experiments in (2.2.2) (Fig. 10, Fig. 11) and (2.2.3) (Fig. 12, Fig. 13) are symmetric.

3 Mathematical summary

Above two cases of thought experiments - two events observed by a single observer and - one event observed by two different observers consist of several sub-experiments in which we have calculated the times t_1 and t_2 . All these variations lead to a more general formula for the calculated time:

$$t_i(E) = \frac{d}{c \pm v}. \quad (11)$$

This formula explicitly depends on the direction of motion of the inertial reference frame and on whether the scenario involves two events observed by one observer or one event observed by two observers.

Note! All thought experiments we have analyzed above are such in which the calculated times t_1 and t_2 show us that:

- the two events E_1 and E_2 are simultaneous in an absolute sense for the observer O or
- the event E is simultaneous in an absolute sense for both observers O_1 and O_2 .

4 Conclusions

Simultaneity is defined as follows:

- **Mathematical definition:** Two events E_1 and E_2 are simultaneous in a certain reference frame if they have the same time coordinate t in that frame: $t(E_1) = t(E_2)$
- **Empirical observation:** An observer can only determine the nature of simultaneity if they have information about both the location and time of each event.

If an observer precisely measures the locations and times of two events, it can be determined whether **the events are simultaneous in an absolute sense**.

Or

If two observers can precisely measure both the location and time of an event, they can determine whether the event is **simultaneous for both of them in an absolute sense**.

If it is not possible to measure the location where the event occurred and the time when the event occurred, one cannot use the information about the event for any meaningful discussion!

5 References

1. Newton, I. (1687). *Philosophiæ Naturalis Principia Mathematica*. London: Royal Society.
2. Einstein, A. (1905). *Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper*. *Annalen der Physik*, 322(10), 891-921.
3. Poincaré, H. (1898). *La mesure du temps*. *Revue de Métaphysique et de Morale*, 6(1), 1-13.
4. Slowak, J. (2022), *Light - The Absolute Reference in the Universe* (4th ed.). Books on Demand, Stockholm.